

Effect of strontium oxide (SrO) on the microstructure and bioactivity of melt derived bioactive silicate glass

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Bioactive glass 46.1 SiO₂ 24.4 Na₂O (26.9-x) CaO 2.6 P₂O₅.xSrO (x = 0, 2, 4, 6 mol%) have been prepared using the conventional melting and annealing method. The glass samples were characterized by Density measurement, Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transformed Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) with Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analysis (EDX). Bioactivity of the glass was measured by SEM with EDS, pH measurement and ionic concentrations analysis after immersion in SBF solution for different days at 37.5°C.

Experimental results showed that SrO substitution for CaO in the glass increased glass density and molar volume whereas oxygen density was decreased. The glass transition temperature and crystallization temperature were decreased with increase in strontium oxide substitution. The XRD and FTIR spectra showed the formation of the crypto crystalline hydroxy apatite (HA) on the surface of bioactive glass samples after immersing in SBF for 14 days. SEM of the 14 days immersed sample shows the formation of cotton ball like HCA layer on the glass. EDS analysis also confirmed the formation of HCA layer. Effect of strontium oxide substitution on the pH, silicon ion concentration and the weight loss after SBF immersion of the different glass samples are discussed.

Keywords: Bioactive glass, strontium substitution, oxygen density, molar volume, bioactivity.

Introduction

Bioactive glasses are a class of biomaterials generally based on amorphous silicate compounds¹. Hench and co-workers were the first to discover in 1969 that bone can bond chemically to certain glass composition. This group of glass has become known as bioactive glass based on the Na₂O-CaO-P₂O₅-SiO₂ system². One aspect that makes bioactive glasses different from other bioactive ceramics and glass-ceramics is the possibility of controlling a range of chemical properties and rate of bonding to tissues. It is possible to design glasses with properties specific to a particular clinical application.

Strontium is an abundant and widely distributed element in the geosphere, natural water and human tissues³. The amount of Sr in the skeleton is only 0.335% of its Ca content⁴. The biological effects of strontium are related to its

chemical similarity to calcium and other elements in group 2A of the periodic table. Its similarity to calcium and bone-seeking behaviour, strontium accumulates to a higher degree in bone, can displace calcium in hard tissue metabolic processes and at high concentrations interferes with normal bone development⁵. Strontium containing glasses have been actively studied due to the beneficial effect of bone growth introduced by strontium ions and SrO does not exert any cytotoxic effect on cell⁶⁻⁹. It was also observed that in alkali free bioglass with different SrO content, substituting CaO upto 10 mol%, retardation of apatite formation onto glass surface was observed above 5 mol% SrO content without significant structural changes glass^{10,11}.

However, to the best of our knowledge, no detailed microstructural studies on the effect of small amount of SrO (0 to 6 mol%) replacing CaO in 45S5 melt derived glass has been reported till date. In the present study, the partial re-

placement of CaO by SrO in the 45S5 bioglass (upto 6 mol%) is thoroughly studied with respect to oxygen density, micro-structural analysis and *in vitro* bioactivity.

Experimental

Preparation of bioactive glasses:

Series of samples in 46.1 SiO₂ 24.4 Na₂O (26.9-x) CaO 2.6 P₂O₅.xSrO (x = 0, 2, 4, 6 mol%) were prepared from analytical grade fine grained quartz [SiO₂] (Loba Chemie), anhydrous sodium carbonate (Merck) [Na₂CO₃] and anhydrous calcium carbonate (Merck) [CaCO₃]. P₂O₅ was added in the form of ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate (Merck) [NH₄H₂PO₅] and SrO was added in the form of strontium carbonate (Loba Chemie) [SrCO₃]. The compositions and the batch code of bioactive glasses are given in Table 1. The weighed batches were melted in Pt-Rh crucibles for 2 h in an electric furnace at the temperature 1400°C. The homogeneous melt were cast into preheated cast iron mould of the required dimensions. The prepared bioactive glass samples were directly transferred to programmable muffle furnace at the temperature 450°C for annealing. After 1 h, the muffle furnace was left to cool to room temperature at a rate of 30°C/h. The annealed glass samples were characterized by Density measurement, X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) with Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analysis (EDX).

Table 1. Composition (mol%) and batch code

Sample code	SiO ₂	CaO	Na ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	SrO
Sr-0	46.1	26.9	24.4	2.6	0
Sr-2	46.1	24.9	24.4	2.6	2
Sr-4	46.1	22.9	24.4	2.6	4
Sr-6	46.1	20.9	24.4	2.6	6

Density measurement:

Archimedes principle was employed to obtain the density of bioactive glass samples using xylene as buoyant (0.87 g/cc). All the weight measurements have been made using a digital balance (Mettler Toledo, Model: CH 8609, Switzerland) having an accuracy of ±0.0001 g.

Molar volume calculations:

The molecular weight of the glass was also calculated and using these molecular weights and density, the molar volume of the glass samples was calculated from the

expression: $V_m = M/\rho$. Here, V_m is molar volume, ρ is the density of the sample and M is the molecular weight of the sample.

Oxygen density (ρ_{ox}) was calculated by dividing the mass of oxygen atoms present in one mole of glass, m_o , which is constant in both glass series by the molar volume of the glass, V_m . $\rho_{ox} = m_o/V_m = M_o \cdot (2xSiO_2 + 5xP_2O_5 + xCaO + xSrO + xN_2O)/V_m$ where M_o is the atomic weight of oxygen and x the molar fractions¹².

Differential thermal analysis:

Differential thermal analysis measurement (Shimadzu DT40) was carried out on powdered bioactive glass samples (75 microns) which were examined up to 1000°C using a powdered alumina as a reference material and the heating rate was 10°C min⁻¹.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD):

The crystalline phase was identified by using X-ray diffraction analysis (PW 1830, Panalytical), the bioactive glass samples were ground to 75 microns and the fine powder was subjected to XRD analysis using Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2 θ range between (20° and 70°) with a scanning rate of 1°/min.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR):

The powder samples were examined by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy by the use of a spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer spectrum two, USA). For IR analysis, 1 mg of the powder samples were carefully mixed with 100 mg of KBr and pelletized under vacuum. Then the pellets were analyzed in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM):

The samples were coated with platinum (Pt) by sputtering (Q150T ES, England) and then the microstructures were observed using a scanning electron microscope (ZEISS EVO^R 18 Special Edition, England).

Preparation of SBF:

The SBF solution was prepared by dissolving reagent-grade NaCl (Merck), KCl (Merck), NaHCO₃ (Merck), MgCl₂.6H₂O (Merck), CaCl (Sigma-Aldrich), KH₂PO₄.3H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich) and Na₂SO₄ (Merck) into double distilled water (Merck) and buffered at pH 7.4 with hydroxymethyl aminomethane (TRIS) (Merck) and HCl 1 N at 37.5°C. The composition of the SBF solution is given in Table 2¹³.

Table 2. Regents for preparing SBF (pH 7.4, 1 L)

Sl. No.	Reagent	Amount
1.	Double-distilled water	750 mL
2.	NaCl	7.996 g
3.	NaHCO ₃	0.350 g
4.	KCl	0.224 g
5.	K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	0.228 g
6.	MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.305 g
7.	1 M-HCl	40 mL
(About 90% of total amount of HCl to be added)		
8.	CaCl ₂	0.278 g
9.	Na ₂ SO ₄	0.071 g
10.	(CH ₂ OH) ₃ CNH ₂	6.057 g

In vitro studies in SBF:

In vitro studies were carried out by soaking the samples (1.0 g) in 50 ml of SBF solution at 37.5°C for intervals of 0 (without soaking in SBF) and 14 days. After soaking, the powder was filtered, rinsed with double distilled water, and dried in an oven at 110°C for 24 h before analysis by FTIR and XRD and SEM-EDX.

pH measurement:

The pH of bioglass powder sample (1.0 g) was soaked in 50 ml of SBF solution at 37.5°C for different time period and the pH was measured using Orion (Star A214) Thermo Scientific pH meter. pH values have been recorded for different time (1, 3, 7, 14 and 21 days) periods at a fixed time interval.

Ionic concentrations analysis:

The ionic concentration of silica of the SBF solution due to soaking of the glass samples for 7, 14 and 21 days was measured calorimetrically by UV-Vis Double beam spectrophotometer (AU 2701).

Solubility test by measurements of weight loss (%):

The degree of solubility of the prepared glass powder samples was obtained by measurements of their weight loss in simulated body fluid (SBF) solution at 37.5°C for the time period 1, 3, 7, 14 and 21 days.

Results and discussion

Density measurement:

The molar volume, density and oxygen density of the rectangular samples are shown in Table 3. Due to larger size of ions (Ionic size of Sr²⁺–118 pm and Ca²⁺–100 pm), the substitution of SrO for CaO results in larger molar volume of the

glasses. Meanwhile, Sr is heavier than Ca with atomic weight of 87.62 and 40.078 g mol⁻¹ respectively. Therefore, the weight of the unit cell also increases with substitution of SrO in glass. The increase in unit cell weight dominates over increased unit cell volume, leading to linear increase density with SrO substitution¹⁴. The density varied from 2.76 g/cc to 2.87 g/cc and molar volume from 22.29 to 22.46 cm³/mol (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Variation of density and molar volume of different annealed glasses.

Oxygen density was calculated to measure the compactness of the glass network. The oxygen density decreases with strontium substitution indicating an expansion of the glass network and a less rigidly bonded glass network (Fig. 2). This is due to the larger Sr²⁺ cation attracting non-bridging oxygen less readily than Ca²⁺ cation⁹.

Fig. 2. Oxygen density as function of strontium oxide content.

Differential thermal analysis:

The DTA thermograms of the glasses recorded at the heating rate of 10°C/min is shown in Fig. 3. The glass transition temperature and crystallization temperature is controlled by the nature and proportions of the glass forming oxide constituents. The ability of some cations to build glass forming units or to be act as modifiers in interstitial positions in the glass structure must also be considered. The DTA data of all the glasses showed onset of first endothermic (T_g) in the 530–453°C temperature range. One exothermic peak (T_c),

Fig. 3. Differential thermal analysis (DTA) plots of different bioactive glasses.

which is detected in each glass, indicating crystallization reaction in the glasses, is also observed. The glass transition temperature (T_g) and crystallization temperature (T_c) were decreased by the addition of SrO at the expense of CaO in the glass compared with that of the base glass Sr-0. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the Sr-4 and Sr-6 glass sample were not properly identified. Greater radius and lower field strength of Sr^{2+} compared to Ca^{2+} is likely to give a glass with weaker bonds⁷. This could be attributed to the fact that increased disruption of the glass network may be due to the presence of slightly larger Sr^{2+} cation, as well as due to weaker Sr-O bond strength¹⁵. This result is in consistent with the expansion of the glass network determined from the oxygen density result (Table 3) and a less rigidly cross-linked glass network. The expansion of the glass network results in the weakening of the glass network⁹. Peterson *et al.* suggested that the glass transition temperature decreases with decreasing the field strength of the cation¹⁶. [Field

Table 3. Density of bioactive glasses

Sample	Density (g/cc)	Molar volume (cc/mol)	Oxygen density (g/cc)
Sr-0	2.7614	22.2872	1.1235
Sr-2	2.7988	22.3300	1.1214
Sr-4	2.8340	22.3884	1.1184
Sr-6	2.8678	22.4566	1.1150

strength at distance of oxygen anions for Sr^{2+} and Ca^{2+} are 0.28 and 0.33 respectively]¹⁷.

X-Ray diffraction analysis:

The bulk glasses were optically transparent after melting and casting. Powder X-ray diffraction study also showed the glasses to be amorphous and free of any significant crystals (not shown). Fig. 4 shows the XRD plots of the bioactive glass samples soaked in the simulated body fluid (SBF) solution for 14 days. X-Ray measurement of the parent (Sr-0) glass sample and strontium containing glass samples (Sr-2, Sr-4, Sr-6) indicate the formation of tiny peak at 31.9° characteristics to crypto crystalline hydroxy apatite (HA) [PCPDF#: 74-0565]¹⁸.

Fig. 4. The XRD plots of the bioglass samples soaked in the simulated body fluid (SBF) solution for 14 days.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) absorption spectroscopy:

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) absorption spectroscopy of bioactive glass samples before soaking in SBF solution:

The FTIR of the glasses are shown in Fig. 5. The spectra

Fig. 5. FTIR transmittance spectra of different bioglasses before SBF immersion.

show transmittance bands at 712 to 741 cm^{-1} is assigned to the symmetric Si-O-Si stretching vibration of non-bridging oxygen atoms between SiO_4 tetrahedron¹⁸. The band at 475–486 cm^{-1} is assigned to Si-O-Si bending which is attributed to normal vibration modes of Si-O in SiO_4^{4-} group indicating the presence of amorphous silicate. Band peaking at 1024 cm^{-1} attributed Si-O-Si asymmetric stretching in $[\text{SiO}_4]^{4-}$ units. 45S5 (Sr-0) bioactive glass shows the broad peak at 1430 cm^{-1} before immersion in SBF which can be assigned to the (CO_3^{2-}) band of carbonates adsorbed on the surface of glass and carbon dioxide present in the atmosphere. For the Sr-containing glasses (Sr-2, Sr-4, Sr-6) the carbonate species adsorbed on the glass surface is indicated through the presence of a broad peak at 1437, 1434 and 1440 cm^{-1} which are attributed to Ca^{2+} coordinated carbonate species adsorbed on the glass surface and carbon dioxide present in the atmosphere¹⁹. No significant change in the FTIR bands could be recorded with progressive replacement of SrO for CaO. This suggests that there are the same Si-O bonds in each glass. This information confirms the fact that all the substitutes glass has essentially same structure and network connectivity. Bulk structure of common melt-derived bioactive composition is dominated by interconnected chains of Q^2 silicate tetrahedron (the Q^n notation denotes a tetrahedron with n bridging oxygen (BO_s)).

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) absorption spectroscopy of bioactive glass samples after soaking in SBF solution:

Fig. 6 shows the corresponding transmission FTIR analysis of bioactive glass samples after immersion in SBF solution for 14 days. After immersion in SBF solution for 14 days, the P-O at 1052 cm^{-1} increased largely indicates formation of Ca-phosphate layer on the samples. Higher intensity of this band in Sr-0 compared to the other Sr containing glass sample are observed. Here two bands at 560 and 600 cm^{-1} which are of the P-O crystalline bands are absent²⁰. Therefore, this finding also corroborates the powder X-ray diffraction pattern of the SBF immersed glass which shows that well crystalline hydroxyl apatite was not formed. Carbonate absorption bands at 875 and 1421 cm^{-1} are also observed suggest the formation of a carbonated hydroxy apatite layer²¹. The bands observed at 1641 and 3442 cm^{-1} in the spectra are attributed to presence of OH group²².

Fig. 6. FTIR transmittance spectra of different bioglasses after immersion in SBF solution for 14 days.

pH measurement:

The average pH values of the solution as function of immersion time is plotted (Fig. 7). The pH for samples with a constant mass of glass to volume of SBF ratio was maintained. The pH of the SBF solutions increase with time and with increasing strontium content in the glass for each soaking time⁷. The mechanism of HCA formation can be assessed by pH behaviour of SBF after immersion of the samples. The pH behaviour of all the bioactive glasses has shown similar

Fig. 7. pH behavior of the SBF solution after immersion of the bioactive glass samples for different time periods.

trends. The increase in pH actually signifies the reduction in concentration of due to the replacement of metal ions in the glass and subsequent production of OH^- ions due to breaking of siloxane bond. It has been observed that pH rapidly was increased in first 72 h. Highest pH was observed with 4 mol% SrO containing glass (Sr-4) after 7 days immersion. But in case of (Sr-0) glass maximum pH was observed after immersion of 14 days. The reduction of pH in SBF is due to the formation of precipitation of calcium phosphate and carbonate. The uptake of carbonate and phosphate ions shifts the equilibrium $\text{HCO}_3^- \leftrightarrow \text{CO}_3^{2-} + \text{H}^+$ and $\text{HPO}_4^{2-} \leftrightarrow \text{PO}_4^{3-} + \text{H}^+$ towards products side, causing a decrease in the pH²³.

Ionic concentrations analysis:

The effect of replacement of CaO by SrO on the change in degradation rate of glass specimens was measured by Si ion concentration in SBF, shown in Fig. 8. The rate of network disruption (dissolution rate) can be approximated by measuring the change of Si concentration in SBF. Here, the Si ion concentration in SBF of SrO containing bioglass specimen was higher than Sr-free one. The replacement may cause a significant increase in glass solubility due to increasing disorder caused by higher ionic radius of Sr^{2+} compared to Ca^{2+} . The highest concentration of Si in SBF is observed in 4 mol% SrO containing bioactive glass and lowest with Sr-0 glass. The release rate of Si ion into SBF decreased after elapsing a certain period of time probably due to formation of Ca-phosphate layer on the surface of glass which limits

Fig. 8. Silicon ion concentration of SBF solution after immersion of glass samples for 7, 14 and 21 days.

the transfer of Si ion from the bulk of the glass sample into solution¹¹.

Moreover, weight measurement of the soaked granules, indicating that the glass dissolution followed the same trend of the ion leaching (Fig. 9). The weight loss was assumed to be mostly due to ion release and network dissolution by breakage of Si-O-Si-O-Si bonds due to action of OH^- ions at high pH.

Fig. 9. Weight loss (%) of glass samples soaked in SBF solution at 37.5°C as a function of time (days).

SEM-EDS analysis of bioactive glass samples:

Figs. 10 to 13 show the secondary electron (SEM) images and corresponding EDS spectra of the studied glasses

Fig. 10. SEM micrographs of the bioactive glass surfaces before immersion in SBF solution.

before and after soaking in SBF solution. SEM images of the SBF treated glass surfaces show marked changes in microstructure when compared to that of the starting glasses. In general, the smooth surface typical of a dense glass is observed in Fig. 10. Fig. 11 is the EDS spectra of Sr-0 and Sr-4 which reflects the elements of Si, Ca, Na, P, Sr being present on the glass surface before immersion.

Fig. 12 shows the SEM micrographs of bioactive glass samples after soaking in SBF solution for 14 days. A change in surface morphology is observed if compared with the initial surface (Fig. 10) of the respective sample. It is clear from the Fig. 12 that bioactive glass samples which were soaked in SBF solution for 14 days are covered with cotton ball like structure with varying size and shape¹⁸. Overlapping growth (agglomerated) of the cotton balls are observed in strontium containing glasses. The amount of HCA formation in strontium containing glasses specially Sr-4 are much higher than

the parent glass (Sr-0). EDS confirms that the cotton balls are HCA molecules. Particularly the HCA particles in the 4 mol% SrO containing glass is compact and smooth.

The EDS studies reveal the inclusion of phosphorus in the composition of the newly formed layer after immersion of 14 days (Fig. 13). It also shows an increase in the calcium/calcium and strontium content and a decrease in the silicon content with respect to the glass before immersion in SBF. The decrease in Si with increasing Ca/Ca+Sr and P concentration on the newly formed cotton ball layers also indicates the formation of hydroxy carbonate apatite (HCA) layer. The EDS analysis confirms the formation of HCA layer on the glass sample. It is also to be noted that the Sr ions are also detected in the newly formed cotton ball like particles suggesting calcium was partially substituted in HCA to form Sr-HCA²⁴. The Ca/P ratio in this layer of Sr-0 glass (Sr content 0) is 1.499 below the ratio in apatite (1.67). The incorpora-

Fig. 11. EDS of the bioactive glass surfaces before immersion in SBF solution.

Fig. 12. SEM micrographs of the bioactive glass surfaces after immersion in SBF solution for 14 days.

Fig. 13. EDS of the bioactive glass surfaces after immersion in SBF solution for 14 days.

tion of strontium (Sr) into calcium phosphate structure is reported by many researchers due to its presence in calcified bone¹⁵. Here the bioactivity behaviour of the glass sample with SrO/CaO replacements is high as indicated from the EDS pattern after immersion in SBF solution. Significant peaks of calcium and phosphorus as well as short peaks of strontium were detected. This may be attributed to Sr ions substituted for a part of calcium in hydroxyl apatite layer and form $(\text{CaSr})_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$. The $(\text{Ca}+\text{Sr})/\text{P}$ ratio in the Sr-2, Sr-4 and Sr-6 are 1.64, 1.69 and 1.58 respectively. The ratio of $(\text{Ca}+\text{Sr})/\text{P}$ in Sr-4 sample are higher compared with the Ca/P (1.67) in apatite⁸. This may be due to the higher atomic mass of Sr compared to Ca. The highest bioactivity was shown by the Sr-4 samples with 4% SrO.

Conclusion

45S5 bioactive glass with substitution of CaO by SrO upto 6 mol% can be prepared at 1400°C for 2 h by conventional melting quenching followed by annealing process. Substitution of CaO by SrO increases the glass density and molar volume whereas oxygen density is decreased with increasing of SrO. Glass transition temperature (T_g) and crystallization temperature are reduced due to the formation of ex-

panded glass structure after substitution of larger sized Sr^{2+} ions for Ca^{2+} . FTIR and powder XRD study confirms the formation of crypto crystalline hydroxy apatite (HCA) after immersion in SBF solution for 14 days. SEM and EDS analysis confirms cotton ball like morphology on the glass surface as HCA. The weight loss of bioactive glasses indicates the increase in dissolution rate in presence of SrO. Best bioactivity is observed with 4 mol% SrO containing glass where $(\text{Ca}+\text{Sr})/\text{P}$ ratio is 1.69.

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